

Review Article

**Psychosocial Challenges of Covid-19 Patients in Nigeria: Implications for
Counselling**

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Abstract

In January 2020 the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the outbreak of a new coronavirus disease, COVID-19 to be a Public Health Emergency of International concern. WHO stated that there is a high risk of COVID-19 spreading to other countries around the world. In March 2020, WHO made the assessment that COVID-19 can be characterized as a pandemic. WHO and public health authorities around the world are acting to contain the COVID-19 outbreak. However, this time of crisis is generating stress throughout the population. This paper therefore focuses on psychosocial challenges of COVID-19 patients in Nigeria: Implications for counselling. The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a dramatic loss of human life worldwide and presents an unprecedented challenges to public health, food systems and the world of work. The economic and social disruption caused by the pandemic is devastating. The index case of COVID-19 in Nigeria was an Italian citizen that arrived to the country on February 27th, 2020, through Lagos State, Nigeria. The government of Nigeria, through the Federal Ministry of Health has been strengthening measures to ensure an outbreak in Nigeria is controlled and contained quickly. The covid-19 pandemic has produced substantial health challenges from the perspective of both its direct health complications and the disruption to delivery of standard care for issues. Daily exposure to news about COVID-19 may result in a range of responses, such as emotional, somatic, and/or behavioural, and can impact mental and physical health. This has major implications for counselling.

Keywords: Coronavirus, COVID-19, Psychosocial Challenges, Patients, Counselling.

Received: 12/09/20

Accepted: 01/12/20

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203

Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Introduction

A novel coronavirus (COV) is a new strain of coronavirus that has not been previously identified in humans. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Most people who fall sick with COVID-19 will experience mild to moderate symptoms and recover without special treatment. COVID-19 affects different people in different ways. The coronavirus disease 19 COVID-19 is highly transmittable and pathogenic viral infection caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-COV-2), which emerged in Wuhan, China and spread around the world. The intermediate source of origin and transfer to humans is not known, however, the rapid human to human transfer has been confirmed widely. There is no clinically approved antiviral drug or vaccine available to be used against COVID-19 (WHO, 2020).

The outbreak of this new coronavirus disease, COVID-19, was declared in January, 2020 by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern. WHO (2020) further stated that there is a high risk of COVID-19 spreading to other countries around the world. This outbreak was also characterized as a pandemic. The outbreak was trying to be contained by WHO and other public health authorities around the world.

A pandemic is a highly infectious disease that spreads across a large-region or the globe with an amazing rapidity and destruction of human lives. The disease is said to have originated from a relatively small town called Wuhan in China in 2019, that is why it is called COVID-19.

The Federal Ministry of Health in February, 2020 confirmed a coronavirus disease (COVID-19) case in Lagos State, Nigeria. The case, which was confirmed on the 27th of February 2020, was the first case to be reported in Nigeria since the beginning of the outbreak in China in January, 2020. The index case was an Italian citizen who works in Nigeria and had returned from Milan, Italy to Lagos, Nigerian on the 25th, February, 2020. The government of Nigeria, through the Federal Ministry of Health had strengthening measures to ensure the outbreak in Nigeria was controlled and contained quickly. The Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) immediately activated its national emergency operation centre and started working closely with Lagos state health authorities to respond to this case and implement firm control measures.

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Gradually, the disease started spread in to other parts of Nigeria, such as Abuja, Ogun, Kano, Katsina States and so on.

Nigerians were reminded that most people who become infected may experience only mild illness and recover easily, but it can be more sever in others, particularly the elderly and persons with other underlying chronic illness. All Nigerians were advised to take care of their health and hand and respiratory hygiene to protect themselves and others. They are to follow the precautions below:

1. Regularly and thoroughly wash hands with soap and water, and use alcohol-based hand sanitizer in the alternative.
2. Maintain at least one and half metres (5 feet) distance between oneself and anyone was is coughing or sneezing
3. Persons with persistent cough or sneezing should stay home or keep a social distance, but not mix in a crowd.
4. Make sure everyone follows good respiratory hygiene by covering one's mouth and nose with a tissue or into one's sleeve at the bent elbow or tissue when coughing or sneezing. Then dispose of the used tissue immediately.
5. Stay home if one feels unwell with symptoms like fever, cough and difficulty in breathing.
6. Stay informed on the latest developments about COVID-19 through official channels on television and Radio.
7. Avoid handshake, shake elbows instead.
8. Citizens must not abuse social media and indulge in spreading misinformation that causes fear and panic.

The symptoms of COVID-19 according to WHO (2020) include;

- i. Sore throat
- ii. Dry cough
- iii. Fever
- iv. Shortness of breath
- v. Fatigue or body ache
- vi. Nasal congestion or diarrhea

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Accordingly common prevention tips were given buy the information center:

1. When one cannot keep a safe distance from others, mouth and nose mask must be worn.
2. Listen for instructions from one's local government about staying home.
3. Cover coughs and sneezes with elbow or tissue.
4. Eyes, nose or mouth must not be touched
5. Stay at least 6 feet or 2 arms, length from others, otherwise known as maintenance social distancing.
6. Wash hands often and disinfect frequently touched surfaces at home.

COVID-19 (coronavirus) has affected day to day life and has also slowed down the global economy. This pandemic has affected thousands of people, who are either sick or are being killed due to the spread of this disease. The most common symptoms of this pain and breathing problems, and ultimately leading to pneumonia. This, being a new viral disease affecting humans for the first time, vaccines are not yet available. Thus, the emphasis is on taking extensive hygiene protocol, social distancing and wearing of masks and others. Because of the spread of this virus, Nigeria has banned social gatherings of people. There has been locking down of people and enforcing strict quarantine to control the spread of this virus.

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic may be stressful for people. Fear and anxiety about this new disease and what could happen can be overwhelming and cause strong emotions in people generally. Public health actions, such as social distancing, can make people feel isolated and can increase stress and anxiety. However, these actions are necessary to reduce the spread of COVID-19. Coping with stress in a healthy, way will make everybody and the community stronger. According to CDC (2020) stress during an infectious disease out-break can sometime cause the following: fear and worry about one's and beloved one's health, financial situation or job. There can be changes in sleep or eating patterns. Also, there will be difficulty sleeping or concentrating. Furthermore there will worsening of chronic health problems and mental health problems and mental health condition. Finally, increase in substance abuse.

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NCDC (2020) explained the day to day body condition of person with COVID-19 infection to Nigerians as follows:

Days 1-3:

- i. Symptoms almost similar to a common cold.
- ii. Slight sore throat
- iii. No fever, no tiredness, normal appetite

Day 4:

- i. Slight sore throat, body ache
- ii. Hoarse voice
- iii. Body temperature around 36.5°C
- iv. Slight loss in appetite
- v. Slight headache
- vi. Minor diarrhea or indigestion

Day 5:

- i. Sore throat, hoarse voice
- ii. Slight fever between 36.5 to 36.7°C
- iii. Weakness of body, joint pain

Day 6:

- i. Slight fever, around 37°C
- ii. Cough accompanied by mucus or dry cough.
- iii. Sore throat when eating, talking or swallowing
- iv. Fatigue, nausea
- v. Occasional breathing difficulty
- vi. Pain in finger
- vii. Diarrhea, vomit

Day 7:

- i. Fever higher, between 37.4 – 37.8°C
- ii. Cough with sputum
- iii. Body ache and headache
- iv. Diarrhea becomes more severe
- v. Vomit

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Day 8:

- i. Fever between 38⁰C or higher
- ii. Breathing difficulties, chest heavy
- iii. Cough continuously
- iv. Headache, joint and hip pains

Day 9:

- i. Symptoms worsen
- ii. Fever higher
- iii. Cough more persistent, more severe.
- iv. Breathing difficult and laborious

The Nigeria Centre for Disease Control stressed further by saying that at this time, blood test and X-ray examinations of the lungs are required. People should wear a mask, pay attention to hygiene, wash hands diligently, avoid crowds, and cancel trips, both local and international.

The coronavirus disease, (COVID-19) pandemic has produced substantial health challenges from the perspective of its direct health complications and the disruption to delivery of standard care for individuals with a range of acute and chronic health issues. Also, the widespread application of social isolation initiatives in all cities of Nigeria raise the potential for significant mental health consequences and psychosocial impacts. In addition to an increasing incidence of anxiety, depression, suicidal ideation and post-traumatic stress, the pandemic may also witness an increase in substance abuse, domestic violence and relationship discord.

In a developing country like Nigeria, where the health care system is already overburdened, surges of COVID-cases are likely to provoke acute anxiety, irritation and stress among the health personal and the citizens. This might be compounded by the inadequate medical supply of required hand hygiene tools as acknowledged by Biswas and Chatterjee (2014). Along with its high infectivity and fatality rates, the 2019 Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) has caused Nigeria and the whole world psychosocial impact by causing mass hysteria, economic burden and financial losses. The disease itself, multiplied by forced quarantine to combat COVID-19 applied by nationwide lockdowns, can produce acute panic, anxiety, obsessive behaviours, hoarding, paranoia, depresses, and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) in the long run (Dubey, Biswas,

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Ghosh, Chatterjee, Lhiri and Lavie, 2020). This unpredictable, fast spreading infectious diseases has been causing the universe at large and Nigeria in particular awareness, anxiety and distress, all of which according to WHO (2020) are natural psychological, responses to the randomly changing condition (Kluge, 2020). In confirmation of the above, Barbisch, Koeing and Shih (2015) and Jeong, Yim, Song, Min, Cho and Chae (2016) reported that psychological impact of quarantine can vary from immediate effects like irritability, fear of contracting and spreading infection top family members, anger, confusion, frustration, loneliness, denial, anxiety, depression, insomnia, despair, to extremes of consequences, including suicide.

Daily exposure to news about coronavirus may result in a range of responses such as emotional, somatic, and/or behavioural stress. And this can impact mental and physical anger, sadness and denial. It is normal to feel anxious and uncertain about one's health during an outbreak of a disease like COVID-19. Getting more information about the virus outbreak from social media may make one feel angry about the situation and how one's life is affected by the virus outbreak. Also, this time around, sadness may set in. one may feel more pessimistic than usual, or feel less motivated in general, which can introduce less concentration in life. There may likely be denial syndrome. These are issues that counseling can help to address. The COVID-19 pandemic further brought many changes on individual's normal ways of living resulting to many uncertainties, stressful changes in daily routines including social distancing and isolation, loss of jobs and consequent financial pressures. These changes again bring untold stress/hardship to many individuals during the pandemic.

Psychologist and Counsellors also came up with a list of advice that are directly related to maintaining good mental health during COVID-19 pandemic. These include the following:

- i. Isolating yourself from news about the virus.
- ii. Don't look out for death toll.
- iii. Don't look for additional information on the internet, it would weaken your mental state.
- iv. Avoid sending, fatalistic messages on the virus. This is because some people don't have the same mental strength as you have.
- v. Spend your time creatively and fruitfully learning something new.

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- vi. Your positive mood will help you to protect your immune system, the negative thoughts only weaken your immune system.
- vii. Most importantly, firmly believe that we will be safe and use will overcome this,
- viii. Don't panic, stay positive. Stay safe everyone.

Beyond Blue (2020) from positive psychology reminds people to remind themselves that this pandemic season is a temporary period. That the isolation, the restrictions on freedom, the health threats, and also the massive unemployment will not last forever.

The Nigerian Psychological Association (NPA) also went into an action immediately by constituting a 27 member COVID-19 National Response Committee and developed a National Response Protocol and factsheet. In addition, a COVID-19 research committee was constituted that identified 14 research duster areas that are ongoing. It also directed state chapters of the Nigerian Psychological Association to constitute their responses committees in line with some guidelines. These committees have been helpful at the state level in supporting the fight against the pandemic.

Beyond media engagements to enlighten the public on the appropriate safety and prevention measures, some of the discussion focused on policy reviews to support the efforts of the government and to reduce fear, feelings of distress and hopelessness. And to encourage the people, assuring that with the appropriate adjustment, they will survive the pandemic as they did they Ebola virus. There were also programs geared towards raising awareness on the areas of increased risk as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and the consequent lockdown. Domestic violence, Cybercrime, substance use disorders, unemployment especially among daily income earners, mental illness especially depression, anxiety disorders and posttraumatic stress disorders were some of the areas of focus. Above all, a free tele-psychological services team was constituted to provide free telepsychological services to needy members of the public in a bid to bring psychological services to the public.

Available Interventions

The following interventions from a range of therapies were made available. The choice could depend on the symptoms most prominent or troubling to the client.

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Psychosynthesis and mindfulness:- One of the teach distressed clients is often that of disidentification-a two-step process consisting of first identifying with the stressor and then misidentifying from it. The skill is paralleled by the mindfulness process called diffusion. Here, the person practising the skill first fuses (identifies) with the feared thought and then distances himself from it (disidentifying or defusing) by creating an observer self. This self-watches the client consumed with fear or worry; but from some distance where the worrisome thought is not as potent. Disidentification and diffusion create a more spacious psyche which affords clients the ability to see their threat level decreases (Assagioli, 1973/ 1984; Harris, 2009).

CBT (Cognitive Behavioural Therapy) and the reframe:- In CBT-based psychologies, the practitioner works to help the client reframe limiting, unhelpful, and/or irrational thoughts, replacing them with more adaptive, realistic ones. Thus, thoughts such as “I am sure I will lose my job in this pandemic, and I will never work again are reviewed” and evidence is sought for them. Even if the person is working in an industry is no evidence to suggest that these industries will not roar into life again when lockdowns are lifted up. Beyond that, the client can be probed to examine if he has ever lots a job before, for whatever reason. If so and the person has been working recently, there is clear counter-evidence to the assertion, I will never work again (Beck & Weishaar, 1995).

Solution-focused therapy:- In this therapy, the practitioner helps the client to focus on solutions to the current problems (Ackerman, 2017). Beyond that, the practitioner can probe for how the client may have coped with situations that were similar in the past. Here, the therapists, and their clients consistently collaborate in identifying goals reflective of clients’ best hopes and developing satisfying solutions.

Mindfulness and medication:- One good method therapist could employ to help the clients is mindfulness practice and medication. Clients can be urged to use it in controlling the mind when things are out of control. It has been scientifically proven to improve well-being, reduce anxiety, stress, blood pressure and chronic pain. Mindfulness practice and medication improve sleep, and alleviate gastro-intestinal difficulties. Kabat-zina (1991) defined mindfulness as the act of paying purposeful attention to the present experience in a nonjudgmental manner. Progressive relaxations can help the client to relax, centre, and find peace in an agitated world.

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Finding meaning, purpose, and values (MPV):- A primary psychsynthesis tool but widely adopted in many other schools of psychology as well, MPV identification establishes what has ultimate meaning, clarifies what then is one's purpose and enables choosing which values are then enacted (Assgioli, 1973 (1984). It is a powerful antidote to the virus of fear and panic sweeping the globe.

Cognitive techniques for coping:- Other cognitive techniques for coping with fears and anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic include the following as outlined by Peters (2020):

Identifying areas of control:- In understanding that the root if fear is the feeling of being out of control, it can be useful to help clients identify what they are in control of in their lives and have a plan for how they will focus on this.

Diffusing catastrophic thinking:- Clients can be taught that through worrying, they may have conscientiously arrived at some important ways to manage their individual situations. This is because worry in small amounts can have a positive function of helping humans arrive at solutions they otherwise might not have thought of.

Mental anchoring:- This tool can be helpful to sue commit to not rethinking worries and fears. With mental anchoring, clients an work with counsellors to set up a phrase or image that they will call to mind when catastrophic thinking or repeated worries begin to come up.

Maximizing the hopeful moments:- A great way of mobilizing internal client resources it to recommend that in a moment of feeling encouraged, clients write a letter to themselves to read when feeling discouraged or afraid. What would they want the frightened part of themselves to keep in mind? Counsellors can recommend that clients read over this again in a moment when they need it.

Drawing on client strengths:- Another way of contracting the internal resources clients already have is to help them get in touch with memories that they have of time where they get through a frightening situation. This can help them to see that instead of seeking security in certainty about the future, they can focus on the knowledge the overall our certainty lies not in anything external but in our own abilities to cope with each challenge that may arise.

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Fear at an emotional level:- There is also a point at which stress crosses into fear. Fear does not always respond well to reasons. It resides in the emotional part of the brain and so there can be times that in order to reach it, we must address on the emotional level.

Implications for Counselling

The following psychological health tips are made available to people:

1. Acknowledge reactions:- Allow time to reflect on what you are feeling and how you may be reacting to any fears and uncertainties of the future.
2. Create and follow a daily routine:- Maintaining a daily routine can help preserve a sense of order and purpose in one's life despite the unfamiliarity of the situation. Try to include regular daily activities, such as listening to music, spending time being creative.
3. Limit news consumption to reliable sources:- It is important to obtain accurate and timely public health information regarding COVID-19, but too much exposure to media coverage can lead to increased feelings of fear and anxiety. Limit the time spent on news and social media. Pay attention to positive news instead of only focusing on negative and fear-producing reports.
4. Practice grounding techniques and breathing exercise- remind yourself to breathe when you are feeling overwhelmed with anxiety and emotions. Try not to catastrophize and instead focus on what you can control, practice relaxation exercises like deep breathing, positive imagery, muscle relaxation, and so on.
5. Maintain a healthy lifestyle- prioritize getting a healthy amount of sleep, eating well, and so on. Sleep, nutrition, and exercise greatly impact the body's ability to regulate emotions.
6. Follow the protection and prevention tips found on the COVID-19 web page on the st.olaf website and national medical authorities.

Conclusion

Soon after the coronavirus was identified in that famous market in China, myriad of articles began appearing about the physical symptoms that infected people may have. More recently there have been many write-ups identifying the psychological stressors and the symptoms individuals can expect to see as they deal with both the prospect of physical infection. And also the need to isolate themselves in their homes or

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elsewhere, forsaking the regular, normal human interactions. During the current health crises, the greatest psychological challenge facing the world at large is that of the fears triggered by uncertainty.

Uncertainty about how many people will remain healthy, how long the limitations on lives will last and so on. In a time like this, uncertainty is always present in people's lives. But with the advent of COVID-19, this uncertainty feels much more tenuous than usual. When people feel overwhelmed by the fears, counselling therapies and techniques available can help in reducing their distress.

Recommendations

Based on the literature review, the following recommendations were thus made:

1. With the aim of better dealing with the urgent and unmet psychosocial issues of different population domains during this COVID-19 pandemic, a new psychosocial crisis prevention and intervention model should be developed.
2. To protect social media from devaluations, strict government laws and legislations regarding fake news, social media rumors, disinformation and misinformation are to be implemented.
3. During a pandemic, people should be aware of their reactions.
4. Exposure to too much information which can lead to overload and more stress should be limited.
5. Maintain a healthy routine of eating well, sleeping and so on during a pandemic.
6. Physical/social distancing is a proven and effective way or reducing spread of infection during an outbreak. Therefore, physical/ social distancing should be maintained.

References

- Ackerman, C. (2017). What is solution-focused therapy: 3 essential techniques. Positive Psychology Program. Retrieved on 24 January, 2018, from: Website.
- Assagioli, R. (1973/1984). The act of will: A guide to self-actualization and self-realization. Wellingborough: Turnstone Press.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

- Barbisch, D, Koenig, K.L and Shih, F.Y (2015). Is there a case for quarantine? Perspectives from SARS to Ebola. *Disaster Med Public Health Prep.*9, 547-53.
- Beck, A.T. and Weishaar, M.E (1995). Cognitive therapy. In current psychotherapies, 5th Ed., Corsini, & Wedding, Eds. Itasca, Illinois: F.E. Peacock Publishers, Inc.
- Beyond Blue (2020). Looking after your mental health during the coronavirus outbreak. Beyond Blue. Retrieved on 29 March, 2020, from: Website.
- Biswas, P. and Chatterjee, S. (2014). Hand hygiene compliance among doctors in a tertiary care hospital of India. *Indian J Pediatr.* 81, 967-8.
- Dubey, S., Biswas, P., Ghosh, R. *et al.* (2020). Psychosocial impact of COVID-19. Diabetes & Metabolic syndrome: *Clinical research & Reviews.* 14, 779-788. Journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/dex.
- Harris, R. (2009). Mindfulness without meditation. In HCPJ (*Healthcare Counselling and Psychology Journal*), 21-24.
- Jeong, H, Yim, H.W, Song, Y.J, *et al.* (2016). Mental health status of people isolated due to middle east respiratory syndrome. *Epidemiology Health.* 38:e 2016048.
- Kabat-Zinn, J. (1991). Full catastrophe living: Using the wisdom of your body and mind to face stress, pain, and illness. New York: Delacorte.
- Kluge, HNP, Statement. (2020). Physical and mental health key to resilience during COVID-19 pandemic. <http://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/health-emergencies/coronavirus-covid-19/statements/statement-physical-and-mental-health-key-to-resilience-during-covid-19-pandemic>
- NCDC (2020). Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention. Coronavirus Disease. Covid-19.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Peters, E. (2020). Is obsessing over daily coronavirus statistics counter-productive? New York Times.

World Health Organization (2020). Mental health and psychosocial considerations during the Covid-19 outbreak. WHO. Retrieved on 29 March, 2020, from: Website.

<https://www.mtholyoke.edu/counseling/mental-health-coronavirus>

<http://achppi-org/resources/coronavirus>

<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203

Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria